

TEMPERATURE INDUCED STRESSES AND DEFORMATIONS IN COMPOSITE SHELLS

László P. Kollár*

Department of Aeronautics and Astronautics
Stanford University
Stanford, California 94305

ABSTRACT

In this paper simple formulas are presented which can be used to estimate the response of composite plates and shells of arbitrary layout to hygrothermal loads.

The formulas serve two purposes. First, they can be used to calculate directly the stresses, strains, and displacements caused by a temperature and a moisture gradient. Second, the formulas can be used to determine the "effective" thermal and moisture expansion coefficients which are the parameters needed in more accurate numerical (FEM) calculations.

The accuracies of the approximate formulas were assessed by sample problems. In these problems the hygrothermal deformations of cylinders and cylindrical segments were calculated by the present approximate formulas and by an exact, three dimensional analysis. The results of the exact and approximate methods were compared. These comparisons showed that the approximate formulas yield the deformations with a high degree of accuracy.

Key words: temperature, moisture, springback, composite shell, approximate analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION

Consider a composite shell which consists unidirectional fiber reinforced plies. There is no restriction on the orientation of the plies, the laminate can be unsymmetric and unbalanced. The middle surface of the shell can be flat, cylindrical, or any doubly curved shape. The shell is subjected to linear temperature and moisture gradients through the thickness:

$$\Delta T = \Delta T_0 + z\Delta T_1, \quad \Delta c = \Delta c_0 + z\Delta c_1, \quad (1)$$

where z is the coordinate perpendicular to the surface, and z is equal to zero on the middle surface. The aim is to determine the stresses and deformations in the composite shell.

The response of a composite shell to a change in temperature (or moisture content) is unexpected; the curvature of cylindrical segments with symmetric layouts changes when they are subjected to a constant change in temperature. This phenomenon is referred to as "springback" (or "spring-forward"). It occurs because of the thickening of the laminate, or more precisely, because of the difference between the in plane and out-of-plane strains in the plies due to the change in temperature and moisture content [1-6].

This effect can be investigated by three dimensional elasticity solutions [5-10], by three dimensional finite element methods (e.g. [2, 4]) or by higher order shell theories [11].

* On leave from the Technical University of Budapest, Department of Reinforced Concrete Structures, Hungary-1521.

Our aim is to determine simple formulas instead of 3-D analysis, based on the classical laminated plate theory [13], to calculate the stresses and strains in composite shells with arbitrary layups subjected to constant and linear temperature and moisture gradients.

Approximate formulas were derived only for cylindrical segments with symmetric layups subjected to a constant change in temperature ([2, 3] see Eq.(10) of this paper), not for unsymmetric, unbalanced, doubly curved shells.

The present summary highlights only the basic concepts of the approximate calculation. For mathematical details the reader is referred to [12].

2. CONSTITUTIVE RELATIONSHIP

The constitutive law for a composite laminated shell is the following [13]:

$$\begin{pmatrix} N \\ M \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} A & B \\ B & D \end{pmatrix} \left\{ \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon^o \\ \kappa \end{pmatrix} - \Delta T_o \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{T0}^o \\ \kappa_{T0} \end{pmatrix} - \Delta T_1 \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{T1}^o \\ \kappa_{T1} \end{pmatrix} - \Delta c_o \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{c0}^o \\ \kappa_{c0} \end{pmatrix} - \Delta c_1 \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{c1}^o \\ \kappa_{c1} \end{pmatrix} \right\}, \quad (2)$$

where N and M are the vectors of forces and moments induced in the shell, A , B , and D are the stiffness matrices, ϵ^o and κ are the vectors of strains and curvature changes of the middle surface. ϵ_{T0}^o , κ_{T0} , and ϵ_{T1}^o , κ_{T1} are the "effective thermal expansion coefficients" [13, 14, 15] for constant and linear change in temperature; and ϵ_{c0}^o , κ_{c0} , and ϵ_{c1}^o , κ_{c1} are the "effective moisture expansion coefficients" for constant and linear change in moisture.

3. METHOD OF SOLUTION

Temperature and moisture affect the deformations of a shell in a similar manner (Eq. 2). For simplicity hereafter we include only the temperature in the analysis with the understanding that the moisture content can be included in an identical manner as the temperature.

The deformations of a laminated composite shell will be calculated using the thin shell approximation [16]. However, the effect of "thickening" due to the change in temperature will be taken into account by modifying the effective thermal expansion coefficients.

The calculation of deformations and stresses will be evaluated in three steps:

- i) First we investigate a plate which has the same layup as the shell in question. We apply a constant change in temperature ($\Delta T = \Delta T_o = 1$) and determine the deformations of the middle surface. These deformations, the in plane strains ($\epsilon_{T0,p}^o$) and the curvatures ($\kappa_{T0,p}$) are the "effective thermal expansion coefficients" of a plate for a constant change in temperature. Then we apply a linear change in temperature ($\Delta T = z\Delta T_1 = z$) and determine the deformations of the middle surface. These deformations ($\epsilon_{T1,p}^o$, $\kappa_{T1,p}$) are the "effective thermal expansion coefficients" of a plate for a linear change in temperature. Due to the above loads the thickness of the plate may change, which causes no additional stresses.
- ii) Second, we modify the effective thermal expansion coefficients calculated for a plate taking into account the effect of the curved middle surface. Note that this modification may vary with position on the middle surface depending on the shell geometry.
- iii) In order to solve for the deformation in a shell with given geometry, loads, and boundary conditions, we have to consider the equilibrium, strain-displacement, and constitutive relationships.

We assume that the effective thermal expansion coefficients of composite plates are given [13, 12], and the displacements perpendicular to the middle surface due to the change in temperature are also known. These are denoted by $\Delta h_{T0}(z)$ and $\Delta h_{T1}(z)$ for a constant and a linear change in temperature respectively [12, 18].

In this paper we will concentrate on the modification of the effective thermal expansion coefficients of a plate due to the curvature effect.

We assume that the material behaves in a linearly elastic manner, the deformations are small, and the normals of the undeformed middle surface remain straight and normal to the middle surface after the deformations.

4. THERMAL EXPANSION COEFFICIENTS OF COMPOSITE SHELLS

For simplicity, we assume that the principal curvatures at the investigated point of the shell are in the coordinate planes. The radii of curvature of the shell are denoted by R_1 and R_2 .

In this section we apply the subscript T instead of T_0 or T_1 , with the understanding that the expressions are valid for both the constant and the linear temperature distribution.

4.1. Effect of thickening of the shell

Due to the thickening, ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 are induced in the laminate. (The induced ϵ_1 is shown in Figure 1.) Assuming that $z \ll R_1$ and $z \ll R_2$ the strains are:

$$\epsilon_{1,h} = \frac{\Delta h_T(z)}{R_1}, \quad \epsilon_{2,h} = \frac{\Delta h_T(z)}{R_2}. \quad (3)$$

where $\Delta h_T(z)$ is the thickening of the laminate. If the deformations are constrained internal stresses arise in the shell, which can be calculated using the laminate plate theory. Applying the opposite of these stresses, the additional deformations of the middle surface due to the thickening can be calculated [12]. These are denoted by $\epsilon_{T,h}^o$ and $\kappa_{T,h}$.

4.2. Effect of stretching of the middle surface of the shell

In the laminate plate theory the strains (ϵ) in a plate can be calculated from the deformations (ϵ^o and κ) of the middle surface:

$$\epsilon = \epsilon^o + z\kappa. \quad (4)$$

These are also the usual approximations of thin shell theory. However, Figure 2 illustrates that the constant strain ϵ_1 is caused by stretching together with a change in curvature of the middle surface. (Note, that different authors use different definitions for the curvature. Flügge [16] defines it as the mathematical change in curvature of the middle surface. Timoshenko [17] defines the curvature as the relative angular displacement of the two opposite edges of a shell element over the element's length. The latter is the definition that we use in this paper.)

It can be shown [12] that the difference between the strains in a plate and in a shell due to the deformations of the middle surface of the shell, $\epsilon_{T,p}^o$ and $\kappa_{T,p}$ are :

Figure 1 Illustration of ϵ_1 caused by the "thickening"

Figure 2 Illustration of a constant ϵ_1 caused by "stretching" and change in curvature of the middle surface

$$\epsilon_{1,s} = -\frac{z}{R_1} (\epsilon_{1T,p}^o + z\kappa_{1T,p}), \quad \epsilon_{2,s} = -\frac{z}{R_2} (\epsilon_{2T,p}^o + z\kappa_{2T,p}), \quad (5)$$

where $\epsilon_{1T,p}^o$ and $\epsilon_{2T,p}^o$ are the first two elements of $\epsilon_{T,p}^o$ and $\kappa_{1T,p}$ and $\kappa_{2T,p}$ are the first two elements of $\kappa_{T,p}$. To get the deformations of the middle surface we have to follow the same steps as in case of the thickening. If we constrain the deformations internal stresses arise. Applying the opposite of these stresses, the additional deformations caused by the stretching of the middle surface can be calculated. These are denoted by $\epsilon_{T,s}^o$ and $\kappa_{T,s}$.

4.3. The Effective Thermal Expansion Coefficients

To get the effective thermal expansion coefficients for a shell we have to modify those of a plate. For constant or linear change in temperature:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_T^o \\ - \\ \kappa_T \end{pmatrix} = \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{T,p}^o \\ - \\ \kappa_{T,p} \end{pmatrix}}_{\text{“plate”}} + \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{T,h}^o \\ - \\ \kappa_{T,h} \end{pmatrix}}_{\text{“thickening”}} + \underbrace{\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{T,s}^o \\ - \\ \kappa_{T,s} \end{pmatrix}}_{\text{“stretching”}}. \quad (6)$$

Let us emphasize that the term due to the “stretching” is necessary only if the shell theory defines the curvature due to [17] and makes use of Eq.(4).

4.4. Approximate Calculation of the Thermal Expansion Coefficients for Constant Change in temperature

We can further simplify the expressions derived in the previous sections for constant change in temperature approximating the displacement $\Delta h(z)$ by a linear function :

$$\Delta h(z) = z\alpha_{z,p}, \quad (7)$$

and neglecting the second (quadratic) terms in Eq.(5). In Eq.(7) $\alpha_{z,p}$ is the average thermal expansion coefficient of a laminate perpendicular to the surface, which is calculated as follows:

$$\alpha_{z,p} = \frac{1}{h} \left[\Delta h_{T0} \left(\frac{h}{2} \right) - \Delta h_{T0} \left(-\frac{h}{2} \right) \right]. \quad (8)$$

This “thickness expansion coefficient” for a symmetric laminate was first derived by Pagano [18].

Applying the above approximation in Eqs.(6) we obtain :

$$\begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{T0}^o \\ - \\ \kappa_{T0} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \epsilon_{T,p}^o \\ - \\ \kappa_{T,p} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 0 \\ - \\ \frac{1}{R_1} (\epsilon_{1,T0,p}^o - \alpha_{z,p}) \\ \frac{1}{R_2} (\epsilon_{2,T0,p}^o - \alpha_{z,p}) \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (9)$$

These simplified expressions are applicable if the out-of-plane thermal expansion coefficients of the plies in a laminate are close to each other, which is true if hybrid composites are not considered.

Note, if the in plane and out-of-plane deformations of a plate caused by the temperature change are the same ($\epsilon_{1,T0,p}^o = \epsilon_{2,T0,p}^o = \alpha_{z,p}$), the last term in Eq.(9) is zero. This is the case for the isotropic materials.

5. SPRINGBACK OF A CYLINDRICAL SEGMENT

The above expression (Eq.9) can be simplified in the case of a cylindrical segment with the radius R , taking into account that $\frac{1}{R_1} = 0, R_2 = R$.

If a cylindrical segment with symmetric layup is subjected to a constant change in temperature the calculation of springback (Figure 3) becomes very simple:

$$S = \Delta T_o (\epsilon_{2,T0,p}^o - \alpha_{z,p}) . \quad (10)$$

This expression is identical to the formula of [2 and 3].

Figure 3 Illustration of springback of an open cylinder

6. SAMPLE PROBLEMS

In order to investigate the accuracy of the derived approximate formulas sample problems were calculated for cylinders and cylindrical segments with different layups and geometries. These results are designated as "APPROXIMATE". The calculated deformations and stresses were compared to the "EXACT" solutions, obtained by the "Segment" code [10]. We compared the results also to those obtained by further simplifications, calculating the deformations and stresses without taking into account the effect of stretching and thickening. These calculations are referred as "PLATE" solutions.

In every example the shell is made out of E-Glass epoxy composite. The material properties are as follows [13]: longitudinal Young's modulus is $E_x = 38.6$ GPa, transverse Young's moduli are $E_y = E_z = 8.27$ GPa, shear moduli are $G_{xz} = G_{xy} = 4.14$ GPa, $G_{zy} = 2.95$ GPa, Poisson's ratios are $\nu_{yz} = 0.4, \nu_{zx} = \nu_{yx} = 0.26$. The thermal expansion coefficient in the longitudinal direction is $\alpha_x = 8.6 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ C$, and in the transverse direction are $\alpha_y = \alpha_z = 22.1 \times 10^{-6} / ^\circ C$.

For brevity, we consider here only cylindrical segments subjected to a constant change in temperature.

First, symmetric, cross ply cylindrical segments were investigated. The data are plotted as a function of the percentage of zero direction plies. (The zero direction is parallel to the axis of the cylinder.) In the approximate calculation for symmetric laminates, the layup has no effect on the deformations; only the ratio of the zero to ninety direction plies affects the effective thermal expansion coefficients. (See the top of Figure 4.) The springback (Figure 3) of the segments are shown in the bottom of Figure 4. The approximate value is the difference between the thermal expansion coefficients plotted at the top of the figure. Using the plate solution, the calculated springback is zero. The exact calculations were performed for two extreme cases, first, if all the zero direction plies are in the middle of the laminate, second, if all the zero plies are at the two outer surfaces of the laminate.

The springback of symmetric angle ply laminates is investigated in Figure 5.

Figure 4 Investigation of a $[0_n/90_{100-n}]_S$ and a $[90_{100-n}/0_n]_S$ laminate. Top: effective thermal expansion coefficients; bottom: springback due to the approximate and exact calculation

Figure 5 Investigation of a $[\phi / -\phi]_S$ laminate. Top: effective thermal expansion coefficients; bottom: springback due to the approximate and exact calculation

Figure 6 shows the effect of the radius/thickness ratio on the springback for a symmetric cross ply segment.

Unsymmetric cross ply laminates were investigated in Figure 7.

In all the above cases we found good agreement between the exact and approximate calculations.

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Figure 6 Investigation of the effect of thickness on the accuracy of springback of a cross ply $[90/0/90/0]_S$ laminate

Figure 7 Calculation of springback on an unsymmetric, $[0/90]_p$ laminate.

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